

PROBLEMS OF ORPHANS AND CHILDREN LEFT WITHOUT PARENTAL CARE IN OBTAINING QUALITY EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract.

Education, recognized by the Convention on the Rights of the Child, is a fundamental human right for all children[1]. All children or students, regardless of their status, should have a quality education that should give them the knowledge, skills and competencies necessary to increase their personal income and increase economic efficiency. Thus, schools are not only useful for the child, but also serve as important resource centers to meet the broader needs of society[2]. In this regard, schools provide children with a safe structured environment, emotional support and adult supervision, the opportunity to learn how to interact with other children and develop social relationships.

Keywords.

social protection, civil society, state, children deprived of parental care, upbringing, public attitude.

Introduction

Investing in health and education improves human capital and is fast is positively related to economic growth. Education is one of the main factors of economic development is one. Education reflects professional and social success in people's lives. Many studies have documented that school success depends on socio-economic status, for example, completeness of the family, economic level, education, living environment, etc. of education Achieving optimal quality is a big problem for any situation, because in school success depends on many factors, such as family socioeconomic and school factors, child health and nutrition and developmental status. About 143,000 worldwide 000 are struggling to care for orphans and millions of abandoned children. Each the child has the right to grow up in a supportive family environment. But all over the world approximately 2.7 million children live in out-of-home care settings and actual the indicator can be much higher[3]. Global politicians are institutionalized orphans and to relocate

abandoned children to their families as soon as possible and institutionalize them promotes the use of care as a last resort[4].

Social protection of orphans and children deprived of parental care is one of the most important tasks of the state and society. Such children are the world today is one of the most urgent problems of modern reality. The growth of social orphanhood, neglect of children, as well as a demographic disaster, to their general crisis in the family is based on The ongoing instability of socio-economic, political life of countries the number of children who are in a difficult life situation is increasing. Among them orphans, socially disadvantaged children and juvenile delinquents, disabled children, runaway children, there are children living in unfavorable environmental conditions.

Research Materials And Methodology

A social orphan is a child who has biological parents, but they are a child for a reason does not educate and does not take care of him. They are legal parents not deprived of parental rights, but in fact raising children and giving them are children who have not fulfilled their duties in terms of providing services.

Orphans, those deprived of parental care and a positive experience in family life children who do not have it cannot build a healthy, full-fledged family. The education system was not perfect Raised in state institutions, he often repeats the fate of his parents, parents deprived of their rights and expands the field of social orphanhood. of this problem according to researchers, 40% of children who leave orphanages are criminals, 40% -drug addicts, 10% commit suicide and only 10% are able to lead a completely independent life[5].

Features of education and upbringing of orphans and children left without parental care assessment, the problem of their support in pedagogy in the first half of the 19th century rose and became particularly relevant in the first quarter of the 20th century. This problem J. Piaget[6], L.S. Foreign scientists such as Vygotsky, D.B. Elkonin[7] studied deeply in science. An orphan and the problem of educational and educational interactions with children left without parental care many researchers in various fields of science and practice: doctors, psychologists, attracted and continues to attract teachers, philosophers, sociologists, social workers is doing. There are many approaches to understanding and solving this problem. Only one thing is certain: educational and educational interaction with orphans and children left without parental care learning relationships is integral.

Researchers in the field of psychology, pedagogy and sociology belong to this category socio-psychological characteristics of children, in particular, reluctance to

adapt to the social environment, Lack of intimate emotional relationships, isolation, despair, dreams are common out of trouble. Relationships with others are ineffective and emotional in terms of content not saturated in terms, that is, they are characterized by little experience of social relations; dependency inclination; low development of individuality, low personal activity; by society resistance to imposed rules and norms. These personal characteristics are in this category does not help students to successfully adapt to independent life. And so, The most important task of school education is that students are not only professionals not only successfully acquire skills, but also become independent individuals need.

Research Results

Thus, according to J. Jersild, "children who grew up outside the family are richly emotional do not have experience: the child's ability to love others is closely related to how much love the child himself has and how it is expressed." A number of authors Craig G., Rean AA.[8] the child's instinctive need to connect with adults they believe there is. Satisfying the child's needs for affection, the body acts like "affective hunger" which is as important as satisfying hunger. This depending on the realization of the need - one of the main needs of the child, his personality, his attitude towards himself is formed. Study of developmental characteristics of children deprived of parental care carried out by many scientists. The influence of parents on the development of the child the founder of the field of study is the English psychologist J.K. Bowlby.

Discussion

A comparative analysis of the behavior of children brought up in orphanages and children brought up in families almost always shows positive mental, emotional and character traits. it is noted that development is stronger in children raised in a family. This is the reason is that the main qualities of a person in childhood are psychological stability, positive, moral orientation, is the period that ensures viability, expediency. A child outside the family development in specific emotional complexes (distrust, aggression, low empathy, etc.) It follows a special path with the formation of unique personality traits. Researchers emphasize the unique characteristics of children in orphanages: they aggressiveness, hypersensitivity, cruelty, stubbornness, hostility, impatience, often neurotic tendencies, attitude difficulties, symptoms of mental stress.

Horoshko L. V. Orphans and parents raised in orphanages highlights the main characteristics of children deprived of care. It is social, are psychological and pedagogical features[9]:

- social, which complicates the process of integrating such children into society. The main characteristics of the characteristics are: independent decision-making, personal lack of life planning and family creation skills. This category of children is often exposed to the negative effects of social processes: addiction, social behavior, drug addiction, alcoholism.

- love and psychological characteristics associated with early parental deprivation characterized by certain signs as a result of a lack of affection. Started as a result of deprivation processes, orphans become indifferent to other people's sorrows, they do not know how to sympathize and empathize. Such children are not sincere, they stand out and has various reasons for celebration; they are indifferent to encouragement and affirmation, there is no response to comments and criticism[10].

- pedagogical problems are related to their pedagogical carelessness. Pedagogical Neglect of children's acquisition of educational materials, moral, political, economic norms and the lack of sufficient abilities to misunderstand spiritual and moral values includes. Disagreement with these norms, such as adolescence, dominance, violence leads to deviant behavior manifested in bad habits. To all this the following features of the emotional-volitional sphere are added: control anger, emotions not get.

Conclusion

It follows from all this that children who are deprived of parental care not only with the innate features of the nervous system and specific characteristics of the individual. It is related to the difficult life experience of the child before he was placed in a boarding school has a complex psychological state. All these psychological processes belong to students directly or indirectly affects socialization. Their successful socialization providing them with knowledge to encourage them, helping them to achieve an independent life skills and competencies should be developed.

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